

3D Printable Platform For Tactile Data Acquisition

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Abstract— Out of need for an efficient and reliable way to acquire data from the interaction between tactile sensors and different textures; in order to contribute to the studies of neuro-morphic processing of tactile feedback signals; the construction of a platform with measurable pressure and computationally controllable horizontal speed was proposed. The platform has a replicable and low budget structure, a large quantity of these parts being 3D printable. The data will be collected by the sensors within the platform, will be send to a computer via microcontroller and used/stored in a database.

Keywords — *Tactile, Sensor, Data, Neuromorphic, Acquisition.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Taking into account the large number of Brazilians who have suffered amputations in recent years, and the increasing demand for prostheses, it was possible to analyze that one of the main causes for giving up the use of these prostheses, especially in the learning phase is the lack of tactile feedback.

The state of available technology was a highly censured factor in abandonment, specifically in the areas of comfort and function. Perceived need emerged as a predominant factor in prosthesis use [1]. When the sensory feedback is biomimetic - designed to mimic natural sensory signals - the participant was able to identify the objects significantly faster than with the use of traditional encoding algorithms that depended on only the present stimulus intensity. Thus, artificial touch can be sculpted by patterning the sensory feedback, and biologically inspired patterns elicit more interpretable and useful percepts [2].

Tactile perception of the material properties in real-time using tiny embedded systems is a challenging task and of grave importance for dexterous object manipulation such as robotics, prosthetics and augmented reality. As the psychophysical dimensions of the material properties cover a wide range of percepts, embedded tactile perception systems require efficient signal feature extraction and classification techniques to process signals collected by tactile sensors in real-time [3].

To better understand the subject, it is valid to know that our hands, or glabrous skin if we want less specific, tactile feedback starts with the neurons called the low-threshold mechanoreceptors (LTMRs), also known as the primary afferents. They are activated by any weak mechanical force applied on it [4]. It's possible to

differentiate LTMRs into two main types, the slow adapting (SA) which are more sensitive to static stimuli, as indentation, being highly sensitive to where the stimulus come and to velocity detection. The other one is the rapidly Adapting (RA) which detect the vibrations of what is being touching the hand and also the slip of held objects [4]. Then, the spikes generated from the primary afferents are concatenated for secondary and tertiary neurons to have the interpretation of the signals done in the somatosensory cortex [4].

Aiming at the physiological needs of users and the presence of more data for the development of software and prostheses integrated with sensory feedback, the construction of a 3D printable platform was required for the testing and data acquisition out of an interaction between a tactile sensor and different textures. The platform has a finger-like support intended to act like a person's finger ruining across a surface. The pressure of the contact will be measured by a pressure sensor placed in parallel of the tactile sensor, the horizontal speed will be controlled by a microcontroller attached in a computer, which will store the data. After the construction the platform will be able to run multiple times per minute, automating the process in a reliable way.

This way it will be possible to use the collected data into the neuromorphic model to simulate the firing behavior of the primary afferents. The model used is the Izhikevich's model, a system of second order differential equations that can, in a simple computational way, reproduce 8 different types of neurons firing behaviors [5], between those it's used the Regular Spiking model to the SA and the fast spiking to the RA for simulate the mechanoreceptors of glabrous skin.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Context and functioning

For the study of different types of textures and how to myoelectrical represent then, the platform was design to represent accurately a person using a tactile sensor on a superior limb prosthesis, the design was done through the *solidworks* software. The proportions were kept minimal, ensuring it would be an easy to build a keep project, ensuring also the replicability in scale if necessary. The thought process is represented by the Figure 1.

Figure 1: Flowchart

The functioning of the platform consists of two axes, the horizontal axis has a movable part that is responsible for carrying the two main sensors that will have the data-out cables, the speed will be adjustable by user input. The vertical part is responsible for applying pressure on the sensors by lifting the textures in a controllable force, that will be also chosen by user input.

B. Building

The building of the platform itself involves components of common use. For the external structure acrylic was used, for the fixation points and the finger-like support 3D printable structures were designed and printed in loco. For the main components metal spindles, bearings and step motors, the tactile sensor used is the 4x4 tactile sensor (Figure 2) that is composed by 16 sensing elements called taxels arranged in 4 rows and 4 columns.

Fig. 2: Tactile sensor

Data from the sensors are acquired by a custom designed sampling board equipped with the microcontroller [6]. The pressure sensor is the FSR402, the mechanism of verification uses an end of stroke sensor.

C. Controlling

For the controlling of the mechanism two STM32 microcontrollers will be used, the code will be written in C# and the functioning of it is based on the correlation between the motor's rotation and the fuses' ratio.

D. Post-acquisition

The storage of data will be a process aside, the tactile and pressure data will be collected in the finger-like support after running across the texture one time and will be send by a microcontroller to a database, that will be later used for the improvement of the pre-existing code that emulates neuromorphic signals. The storage of data will be a process aside, the tactile and pressure data will be collected in the finger-like support after running across the texture one time and will be send by a microcontroller to a database, that will be later used for the improvement of the pre-existing code that emulates neuromorphic signals.

After the data been storage, it will occur a pre-processing and after that it is normalized. With the data normalized, it is possible to segment the data to have the amount of time wanted for the operation.

Then, to reproduce the signal of a primary afferent firing it will be applied 2 different Izhikevich's model [4], the regular spiking to reproduce the SA neurons and the fast spiking for the RA. Repeating the process to generate the 2 signals from all the data that will be used.

III. RESULTS

After the processes of development and improvement, the digital modeling of the platform was finished. All the parts that will be used for the assembly are represented in the Figure 3.

Fig. 3: Solidworks' model

IV. CONCLUSIONS

With the choice of materials, platform design, modeling planning and assembly of parts and components the device could acquire tactile data from whatever texture fitting in its proportions that are compatible with the code already existing. Considering the fact that the platform has not yet been used and considering the limitations of the time required

for acquisition and processing of data. In addition, the specifications of the materials, which do not support applied force of more than 15000 N the estimated that the speed of the interaction between the pressure and tactile sensor, horizontally, will be adjustable varying between 100 mm/s and 600 mm/s and could be constant or variable depending on the user's input. The vertical force will also be controlled by the user's input and could vary between 100 N and 700 N, contributing for the making of a large database for comparison and improvement of the preexisting and relatable works in the field of research.

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